

Small Languages with Transfer

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Abstract

Given a finite set of formal languages $(\mathcal{L}_1, \dots, \mathcal{L}_n)$, one may be interested in analyzing the correspondences of short sentences in one language with coherent sheaves of words in another. In this paper, we work towards the goal of doing so by extending the set-theoretic notion of a “transitive inner model” to the more amenable setting of abstract algebra.

I. Preamble

In the study of *model theory*, there is a notion of an “inner model” of a structure $\mathcal{S}$; succinctly, this is a stationary locale of $\mathcal{S}$ which encodes the following data:

- A representative $\pi_s \times \mathcal{S}$, which is stable
- A relationship $s_i \wr \mathcal{S}$, which is generic
and
- A correspondence, $\text{Cor}(s_i) \rightarrow s \in \mathcal{S}$

The last of these is effectively *topological*; in case $\mathcal{S}$ is defined to be a solid object which is *encompassed* by some group/stack/etc., which is hereditary, we say that $\mathcal{S}$ is the *underlying topology* of a *section* of the parent structure, which is called the profinite site. In this paper, we will be working with the Nisnevich site, remaining partial to the construction of Voevodsky [Tr], in order to avoid unnecessary labor or, to put it roughly, “reinventing the wheel.” We will work in a language of arbitrary order, which bears a nested sequence of substructures:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\{\emptyset\}} \subset \mathcal{L} \subset \mathcal{w} \subset \mathcal{L}^+,$$

where the leftmost item is a *pure urelement*, $\mathcal{L}$ is atomic (letter-like, i.e., “characteristic”), $\mathcal{w}$ is a word, and $\mathcal{L}^+$ is an “extended $\mathcal{L}$ -complex.” An extended $\mathcal{L}$ -complex should be thought of as a polystable fibered manifold, or “multi-language,” whose sheaves are languages, whose stalks are words, and whose relationships are isomorphic with a “bundle” of truth values. In other words, there is an equivalence:

$$\mathcal{L}_m \oplus_{\text{conj}} \mathcal{L}_n \simeq \int_{\mathcal{w}_0}^{\mathcal{w}_n} \frac{\tau(\mathcal{w}_{n!})}{n \otimes (n-j)} = \text{ev}(\mathcal{S})$$

for $j = \sum_0^{n-1} \tau$. The right-hand side of the equality consists in the permutations of the words in a given

“sentence” (here, a short exact series), which is called the “conjugation” of the sentence. Thus, there is

an intrinsic connection between the multipartite $\mathbf{G}_\mathcal{Q}$, which has languages as vertices, and orderings as edges, and the conjugation of a sentence taken over a section of said graph.

In practice, this is extremely difficult to compute, but in theory, it would allow one to assign a variety of truth values to a particular arrangement of words, where the relative position of each is a dependent variable of the function $f(\mathcal{S})$, which is an automorphism $\mathcal{Q}_m|_{\mathcal{S}} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}_{m+n}|_{\mathcal{S}}$.

II. The Nisnevich Site

Let $\mathbf{M}$ be an inner model of a theory $\mathbf{T}$. Here, we take a *theory* to mean a spectrally-enriched category $\text{cat}\mathbf{T}$, together with a set of restriction maps sending every object in $\text{cat}\mathbf{T}$ to a closed subscheme $\mathbf{T}_{\text{SM}}$. The setting for a theory is then, naturally the (large) **Nisnevich site**. Roughly speaking, this is the site for which every representative $\pi_\tau \times \mathbf{T}$ has a canonical (étale) morphism from the category of stacks to a subscheme of a presentable category **SSch**.

Definition 2.0.1 Call a subscheme $\mathbf{T}_{\text{SM}}$ of **SSch** *typical* if for some type $\mathbf{T}$, the inclusion $\mathbf{T}_{\text{SM}}:\mathbf{T}$ holds both locally, whence the necessary restriction to a language $\mathcal{Q}$ is made, and globally, whence it is in the inner model of an extended $\mathcal{Q}$ -complex. Otherwise, we shall call the subscheme “special,” and say that there is an *coherency obstruction*, which we write

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{SM}} \not\rightarrow \mathcal{Q}_{\text{coh}}$$

In general, if such an obstruction exists, then the *strictification* of s fails to provide a good projective module for the measure of s to be realized as a proper conjugation of its subterms. This is to say, only the typical subschemes are amenable to the Nisnevich site, whereby “amenable” we mean that there is a suitable basis object $b \sim s$, which transforms the underlying groupoid of a sentence bearing s into a proper subgroup of its conjugation.

In the large Nisnevich site, not all subschemes are typical. However, this is not the case for the small Nisnevich site, which is by definition finer than its parent. Thus, special objects are manifestations of obstructions to the passage from the global $\mathcal{Q}$ -complex to a local monad, and thus a localization functor in the big Nisnevich site is one which takes sentences in the $\mathcal{Q}$ -complex of a theory and maps them to inner models. The fact that special subschemes exist leads naturally to the following:

Proposition 2.1.0 $\mathcal{Q}^+ \supset \mathcal{Q}_1 \cup \mathcal{Q}_2 \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{Q}_\infty$; in other words, “an extended $\mathcal{Q}$ -complex is more than the sum of its parts.” This is the *gestalt* axiom.

The gestalt axiom tells us that combinations of characters in many separate languages may be used to generate words in sentences with relatively high truth values.

We now define a transfer;

Definition 2.1.1 For a special morphism $s \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}^+$, and a sheaf $\mathcal{O}_x$, say that the morphism is a *transfer* if there is a stalk of $\mathcal{O}_x$ which supports the finite image of s .

Write $\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M}_{a,b})$ for a transfer between two transitive inner models with distinctive representatives π_a and π_b .

Proposition 2.1.2. There is a commutative diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \pi_a & \rightarrow & \pi_b \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ \mathbf{Sch} & \rightarrow & \mathbf{SSch} \end{array}$$

in which the horizontal morphisms are *transfers* (x,y) from $\mathbf{T}$ -stacks to local restrictions of the big Nisnevich site. If we append a terminal object, $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}$, we obtain the following maps:

$$\pi_a \rightarrow \mathbf{Sch}_{\text{coh}} \text{ and } \pi_b \rightarrow \mathbf{SSch}_{\text{coh}},$$

and we define a product

$$\mathbf{Sch}_{\text{coh}} \otimes_{\mathcal{F}} \mathbf{SSch}_{\text{coh}} \rightarrow \tilde{\mathcal{S}}[\tau],$$

which gives us the genuine categorical truth value of the grounded ω -module, which is essentially a fuzzy value in the interval $[[0,1]]$. Equivalently, we can arrive at this value if we take the product

$$\mathbf{Sch}_{\text{Norm}} \otimes_{\mathcal{F}} \mathbf{M}_{a,b} \rightarrow \text{coker}(\mathbf{M})^x;$$

in the second approach, we equip a quasi-separated normal bundle of characters and *foliate* their representation using their respective model weights.

In case of a coherency obstruction, we define the transfer $\text{Hom}(\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M}_{a,b}), \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M}_{b,c}))$ by taking $a \cup \cap_{\mathbf{b}c} \cong \overline{M}$, and take the Grassmanian $\boldsymbol{\theta}(\overline{M})$ to its p th root of unity, giving us the formula:

$$\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M}_{\text{special} \rightarrow k}) = \mathbf{T}_{SM} \rightarrow T_{SM}^{\theta^p}$$

where the right-hand side is a class-level permutation of order $\mathbf{O}(p) \in \log_p \mathbb{Z}$, where p is a sufficiently small prime, say, < 8 . Assuming the morphism to be smooth yields the desired monotone-light factorization

$$(\mathbf{SSch} \circ k) \circ (k' \circ \mathbf{BG}(\mathbf{Nis})) \rightarrow p_i,$$

where p_i occurs in the quadratic expansion of $\mathbf{F}_{\text{RNG}}(p_{\text{red}})$, and where p_{red} is a prime ideal of highest inertia. Thus, by virtue of said inertia, p_i translates to a *semi-coherent* forcing notion, thus forcing the immersion

$$(\pi_i^p(k) \circ \pi_t \times \mathbf{M}) \Vdash \text{ét}\mathbf{M} \hookrightarrow \text{dom}(p_i),$$

such that the closure $\overline{\text{Nis}_{\text{bad}}}$ becomes an $(i-1)$ -fold cover of the stratum containing the dominant coweight of t . Dually, the *compactly generated* (based) portion of the groupoid whose covering deck is $\pi_p(\mathbf{SSch}_{\text{special}})$ is promoted to the status of a uniformizer for a genus-0 section of the big Nisnevich site, which thereby instantiates the solidity of the genuine étale spectrum through the lens of the special locale, thereby resolving the obstruction.

Hence, when $\mathbf{BG}(\mathbf{Nis})$ is finitely supported by $\mathbf{BG}(\overline{\mathbf{Nis}_{bad}})^+$, it is therefore dualizable, and to that effect the structure sheaf of the big Nisnevich site exhibits a relative perversity which enables the conservativity of the extension $\mathbf{M}^+(\mathbf{T})$ of the base theory. We then seek for an ultimate simplification of this theory, which may be found by denoting the descent of the ground model to a generative perverse section as the *exponentiation* $\mathbf{T}^{\text{bad}}(\alpha)$, where α is a parabolic subgroup of the powerset $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{T}_{\mathbf{M}})$ of a theory and its inner models.

III. Connection to language

We have seen how the obstruction of special sentences can be repaired through the easing of the relative strictness of the little Nisnevich site. Specifically, we have illustrated a technique for transforming special sentences into admissible objects in the lax-monoidal category consisting of a certain reduction of typicality. Now, we will resume our discussion of languages.

In specific, take $\mathcal{L}_1, \mathcal{L}_2$ to be fixed languages with uniquely determinate sets of meanings associated to each of a finite list of signs. Let ω_0 be a mutually exclusive element of $\mathcal{L}_2$, such that there is a small presentable sentence in $\mathcal{L}_1$ which accommodates its meaning. Then, we call ω_0 a “loanword” whence there is an immersion

$$\omega_0 \hookrightarrow_{\text{special}} \mathcal{L}_1,$$

and we say of the category in which this inclusion takes place that it is called, properly, $\mathcal{L}^+$.

Assume that there is some étale morphism $\mathcal{L}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_1|_{\text{unique}}$, from $\mathcal{L}_1$ to an inner model consisting of those “pure words” which make up the substance of the vocabulary not borrowed from other languages. Etymologically, such words may be inherited from precedent languages in the family of which $\mathcal{L}_1$ is a normal variety; however, we consider $\mathcal{L}_1$ to be a *proper locale* of such ancestry, and so in the chain of dependencies from $\mathcal{L}_{\text{PRE1}} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_1$, we allow that all of the injections are *Cauchy*, in that they converge absolutely to a generic element with a reasonable agreement with the characteristic norm over $\mathcal{L}_1|_{\text{unique}}$. Then, we see clearly that $\theta(\overline{M}) = \omega_0$, so that the loanword, acting as a discrete module, becomes the Grassmanian of a theory encompassing the transfer $\text{Hom}(\mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M}_{s,\omega_0}), \mathcal{A}(\mathbf{M}_{\omega_0,c}))$, where a is the target language and b is the source of the loanword.

Hence, there is a *Dehn twist*, ω_0^* , which, acting as a motive over the codomain of $\mathcal{L}^+$, forms the necessary *bridge* between the two languages, so that there is a separable compartment of $\mathcal{L}_1$ with a typical embedding from said bridge. Thus, the stack of $\mathcal{L}^+$ includes, as a degenerate category, the *split Nisnevich site*

$$\mathbf{LNis} \twoheadrightarrow \mathbf{SNis}$$

which hosts the new linguistic unit as a basepoint. Further, there is then a delooping,

$$\mathbf{SNis}\{*\} \rightarrow \{*\} \cup \mathcal{L}_1|_{\text{unique}}$$

such that the unit may be integrated (given shape) via the modality $f\{\ast\} \rightarrow \mathfrak{Q}_1$, essentially making the “bad” (perverse) reduction of the host language into an *admissible* proto-site for the pure module which is signified by the twist.

Proposition 3.0.1 There is a short exact sequence $\mathbf{T}^{\text{bad}}(\alpha) \rightarrow f\{\ast\} \rightarrow \mathfrak{Q}_1 \rightarrow \text{ev}(\mathbf{S})$ which allows a special sentence to bypass obstruction in passing from the extended $\mathfrak{Q}$ -complex to the truth evaluation of its conjugation with proper and unique sets of words in independent languages $\mathfrak{Q}_1, \mathfrak{Q}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{Q}_n$

Proof Let α be generated by a representative of the inner model $\mathbf{M}$ of a theory $\mathbf{T}$ encompassing two or more of the languages in the extended $\mathfrak{Q}$ -complex. Then, there is a relationship $\alpha \wr \mathfrak{Q}_m \oplus_{\text{conj}} \mathfrak{Q}_n$ on the semidirect product of languages.

Suppose that this relationship induces a preorder, and rewrite it as $\tau_x | x \leq n$. Then, one has $\alpha \tau_x \mathfrak{Q}^-$. Since we are only working with a subset of $\mathfrak{Q}^+$, we are technically working with the reduction, $\mathfrak{Q}_{\text{RED}}^+$; since the sentence is *special*, i.e., not comparable under τ_x , we pass to $\mathbf{T}^{\text{bad}}(\alpha)$. Through the shape modality, we establish a pointlike character (minimal representation) in the atlas of $\mathfrak{Q}^+$ which agrees with the big Nisnevich site up to inductive colimits. Since the filtered colimits of the individual languages are preserved by $\mathbf{LNis}$, it follows that in restricting ourselves to $\mathfrak{Q}_1$, we preserve colimits. This means that the functor $f\{\ast\} \rightarrow \mathfrak{Q}_1$ is conservative.

Finally, we let $\mathcal{O}_X(\tau_x \mathfrak{w}_0 \wr \mathfrak{Q}_1, \mathfrak{Q}_2, \dots, \mathfrak{Q}_n |_{\text{unique}})$ be the twisted sheaf of truth evaluations over the conjugate structure of the extended $\mathfrak{Q}$ -complex. This gives us that sentences including loanwords are gradable using fuzzy truth values in the interval $[0,1]$, thus completing our proof.

Reference

[[Tr] **V. Voevodsky**, *Triangulated Categories of motives over a field*

[ML] **J.J. Xarez** *The monotone-light factorization for 2-categories via 2-preorders*